

Applications of Psychology in Education

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Abstract

Psychology as a science of human and animal behaviour and cognitive processes has both research and applied orientations. The article discusses applications of Psychology in Education and the contribution of the Psychologists to the field of education. Briefly focusing the work of William James, John Dewey and Edward Thorndike, the psychologists that laid the foundations of Educational Psychology; the article also discusses some of the applications of Psychology in education extending from learning, assessment, motivation to the development, classroom management, special education, and social and emotional learning.

Key Words: Principles of Psychology, Applications of Psychology, Educational Psychology

Introduction

Psychology as a science of human and animal behaviour and cognitive processes has both research and applied orientations. This diverse scientific discipline embraces numerous branches of research like Experimental Psychology, Biological Psychology, Cognitive Psychology, Lifespan Developmental, Personality, Social Psychology), along with the applications of this research in physical as well as mental health and therapies, adjustment issues, industries and organizations, family and relationships, social issues, crime and investigation, education etc. This article focuses on the applications of Psychology in Education.

Rationale

Given to the fact that humans are on the top ladder of evolution, education can transform them in more matured individuals. So, education is an important component and contributing factor the development of an individual. The goal of development is to make the individual more capable and it is also a main goal of education too. Educational psychologists try to make this developmental process as effective as possible by applying psychological principles in imparting education.

Objectives

1. To understand how the principles of Psychology can be applied in the field of education
2. To understand the contributions of some of the leading psychologists to the field of education

Methodology

It is an archival study that discusses applications of Psychology in Education and the contribution of the Psychologists to the field of education.

Discussion

William James, John Dewey and Edward Thorndike laid the foundation of Educational Psychology. In a lecture series "Talks to Teachers",

William James discussed the finest methods of teaching and the use psychological principles for the purpose (James, W.,1958).

John Dewey established the first laboratory of educational psychology in Chicago, USA in 1894 and continued his innovative work at Columbia University. He stalwartly felt that it was an accountability of people to make this world a better place with the help of edification and social transformations. (Williams, M. K. 2017). For him, schools are not only meant for knowledge, but they shall be considered as social institutions that provide necessary opportunities for social interactions; these social exchanges play a prime role in effective education (Flinders & Thornton, 2013). He emphasized students' active participation in learning process. At the same time, he also emphasized the overall development of the students. He envisioned that children should be able to adapt to the world outside school and solve their own problems. Theobald (2009) thinks of Dewey as the most renowned and influential philosopher to influence edification.

Thorndike emphasized assessment and maximizing the intellectual skills of students along with teaching. He initiated scientific research on teaching and learning process and added value to it by proposing three laws of learning. The law of readiness emphasizes learners' readiness and condition to learn (Islam, M. H.,2015). The law of exercise states that teacher can elicit a desirable response by providing multiple opportunities. According to him, the fundamental law of teaching and learning is the law of effect that emphasizes the reinforcement of expected and desirable responses and elimination of unexpected and undesirable responses. Thorndike thought that it was very important on the part of teachers to make the learning activities satisfying so students would give desirable response to learning. (Sears, L.,2007).

According to him, making students interested in learning is also important and it can be done by contiguity, suggestion, imitation, conditioning and selection through rewards and penalties. (Sears, L.,2007).

Psychology has several important applications in the field of education. Understanding how individuals learn, develop, and behave can greatly enhance teaching strategies, classroom management, and student outcomes. Here are some key applications of psychology in education:

Learning and cognition: Psychology helps educators understand how students acquire knowledge, process information, and make connections between different concepts. By applying principles of cognitive psychology, educators can design instructional methods and materials that optimize learning, such as using active learning strategies, incorporating visual aids, and promoting critical thinking skills.

Educational assessment: Psychology plays a crucial role in designing and implementing effective assessment methods. Psychometric principles help educators develop reliable and valid tests and measurements to assess students' knowledge, skills, and abilities. Additionally, understanding concepts like formative and summative assessments can help teachers monitor student progress and adjust instructional approaches accordingly.

Child development: Knowledge of developmental psychology is essential for educators to create appropriate learning environments and tailor instruction to students' developmental stages. Understanding the physical, cognitive, social, and emotional changes that occur during different life stages helps teachers design age-appropriate activities, address individual differences, and support students' holistic development.

Motivation and engagement: Psychology provides insights into the factors that motivate and engage students in the learning process. By understanding theories of motivation, educators can create a supportive and stimulating classroom environment, set meaningful goals, provide timely feedback, and use strategies that foster intrinsic motivation and a growth mindset.

Classroom management: Applying principles from behavioural psychology can assist educators in establishing effective classroom management strategies. Techniques such as positive reinforcement, behaviour modification, and clear expectations help create a positive and structured learning environment, promoting student engagement and reducing disruptive behaviours.

Special education and inclusion: Psychology informs the understanding of diverse learning needs and supports the development of inclusive educational practices. By understanding different

learning styles, cognitive abilities, and exceptionalities, educators can tailor instruction, adapt teaching methods, and provide appropriate support to students with special educational needs.

Social and emotional learning: Psychology highlights the importance of social and emotional factors in the educational setting. Educators can use principles from social psychology to foster positive peer relationships, empathy, and prosocial behavior among students. Additionally, incorporating social-emotional learning (SEL) programs can enhance students' emotional well-being, self-awareness, self-regulation, and interpersonal skills.

Educational psychology research: educational psychologists conduct research to identify effective teaching methods, investigate factors that influence learning outcomes, and explore the impact of educational policies and interventions. Educators can benefit from staying updated on research findings to inform their instructional practices and decision-making.

By applying psychological principles in education, educators can create more engaging and effective learning experiences, promote positive student outcomes, and support the holistic development of learners.

Conclusion

Principles of Psychology and the work of various psychologists have contributed effectively in the field of education. The application ranges from learning, assessment, motivation to the development, classroom management, special education, and social and emotional learning.

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